
SUSTAINABLE HRM AND SUSTAINABLE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS FROM 2010 TO 2025

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ABSTRACT

At the present, governments, corporations, and individuals are working together to advance sustainable human resource management (SHRM) best practices. Which are progressively moving in the direction of sustainable HRM practices. SHRM practices, encompassing green HRM, socially responsible HRM, and triple bottom-line approaches, are examined for their role in fostering a sustainable organizational culture that balances economic, social, and environmental goals. The aim of this study is employed bibliometric analysis to examine and visualize the literature about sustainable HRM and organizational culture. A 478 publications (2010 to 2025) were chosen from Scopus databases that are carefully investigated to produce enlightening outcomes. This bibliometric analysed the data with VOS Viewer software was applied to quantitatively and visually analyse the core study or author, as well as its relationships, by covering all related publications, co-authorship and co-occurrence of Keywords and bibliographic coupling mapping or specific fields relationship between Sustainable HRM and Sustainable organisational culture. The research also provide interesting finding that may be beneficial for industry to develop sufficient sustainable HRM practices which are closely associated with organization culture that create economic, social and environmental impact in various field. The finding showed that there is lack of research in the field of sustainable human resource management with organization culture, it will suggested to explore unified framework for understanding sustainable organization culture in sustainable human resource management.

Keywords— Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM), Human Resource Management, Organization Culture, Bibliometric analysis; VOS Viewer

I. INTRODUCTION

For decades, the concept of sustainability has been a focal point in management discourse. The first official definition of sustainability was provided in 1987 by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) in its report *Our Common Future*, which defined sustainable development as development that “meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” [1]. This definition also introduced the three fundamental pillars of sustainability: environmental, economic, and social dimensions [1]. The WCED highlighted concerns regarding environmental degradation and its socio-economic impacts on global growth. In the corporate sector, sustainability is critical as it allows businesses to pursue long-term development while addressing environmental and social challenges [2].

Sustainable Human Resource Management (HRM) integrates sustainability principles into the strategies, policies, and practices of HRM. This approach seeks to maintain a balance between organizational goals, employee well-being, and broader ecological and societal responsibilities [3]. As the importance of sustainable development rises, organizations across sectors are increasingly emphasizing environmental responsibility, social equity, and profitability in equal measure [4]. Sustainable HRM not only supports organizational objectives but also cultivates a strong organizational culture geared toward continuous improvement [5].

Organizational culture—defined as a shared set of values, norms, beliefs, and behaviours—plays a significant role in shaping company performance [6]. It influences organizational effectiveness, particularly in driving sustainability and efficiency in the workplace [7]. Factors such as size, operational methods, and structural composition further shape the culture, ultimately determining organizational success or failure [8]. Recent research suggests that strong organizational cultures, especially those that promote sustainability, enhance human resource systems and workplace sustainability programs [9].

A sustainable organizational culture refers to values and shared assumptions regarding sustainability that guide corporate practices and decision-making [10]. Such cultures increasingly viewed as crucial to long-term competitiveness and sustainability goals. [11], [12]. They are positively associated with strategic areas like supply chain management and entrepreneurial initiatives [13]. To foster a truly sustainable culture, organizations must understand underlying beliefs and assumptions about sustainability at a deep cultural level [14], [15].

Additionally, a sustainable organizational culture facilitates HRM functions by helping identify, support, and retain high-value employees [16]. Research emphasizes that sustainability practices may manifest differently depending on the organizational context and cultural background [17]. Strong sustainability-oriented cultures help employees internalize sustainable practices, ultimately enhancing commitment and organizational outcomes [18].

The ultimate goal is to promote a sustainable organizational culture that boosts employee performance and long-term retention through the adoption of sustainable HRM practices. However, There remains a lack of integrated research that fully explores the relationship between sustainable HRM and organizational culture. This study aims to bridge that gap by developing a comprehensive understanding of sustainable organizational culture alongside sustainable HRM practices across all organizational levels.

KNOWLEDGE GAP AND RESEARCH QUESTION

Numerous scholars have explored the domain of Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM), focusing on sustainable HRM practices, grounded theory, and the varying facets of SHRM [1]–[3]. Systematic reviews have conducted on sustainable HRM, its practices, and organizational culture. [4]. However, the field remains in its developmental stages. According to Anlesinya and Susomrith, critical contextual and methodological insights are scarce in existing literature, and the influence of boundary conditions and contextual elements on SHRM practices and outcomes is still not well-understood [5].

Richards examined various SHRM dimensions, including characteristics, practices, and outcomes, and categorized SHRM into three strands: built ergonomics and environment, HRM and employee engagement, and sustainable working lives. He emphasized the need to study cultural variation in SHRM practices across different industries and regions [6]. Qamar et al. analysed the theoretical, contextual, and methodological trends in SHRM and its connection to employee well-being, identifying a lack of coherence in the field that necessitates further integrative research [7].

Gomes et al. conducted a bibliometric review using data from Web of Science, analysing 27 articles published between 2019 and 2022. Their study revealed several unexplored areas in the relationship between sustainable HRM and employee attitudes [8]. Similarly, Nida et al. identified an upward trend in scientific output and suggested the use of tools such as VOS Viewer to analyse global research expansion, though the field still needs refinement, particularly concerning social, economic, and environmental aspects [9].

Putri emphasized the importance of identifying research novelty and conducting deeper analysis to uncover new correlations and influencing factors [10]. Ramgolam et al. highlighted that while SHRM has gained some traction, it still requires integration with broader sustainability principles [11].

Despite increased attention, SHRM and Sustainable Organizational Culture (SOC) remain nascent fields. Multiple scholars have underscored the theoretical and contextual complexity, as well as a lack of generalization in the existing literature [12]–[22]. To address these gaps, the current study employs bibliometric analysis as a methodological approach to evaluate the state of research and to provide future research directions. Bibliometric analysis enables scholars to map evaluation trends, synthesize relevant studies, and identify thematic gaps in the literature [23], [24].

The present study aims to enhance understanding of the relationship between SHRM and sustainable organizational culture by identifying emerging themes, trends, and research priorities. Accordingly, this research seeks to answer the following questions:

- What is the volume, production, and distribution of authors' work in the area of Sustainable HRM and Sustainable Organizational Culture?
- What are the major emerging trends, keywords, patterns, and themes in the literature on Sustainable HRM and Sustainable Organizational Culture?
- What are the main elements of future directions on Sustainable HRM and Sustainable Organizational Culture?

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The data for this study extracted from the Scopus database, covering the period from 2010 to 2025. As suggested by Falagas et al., selecting a reliable and comprehensive database is the first crucial step in conducting a well-planned bibliometric analysis, and Scopus offers broader journal coverage than many other databases [25].

A. AREA OF THE SEARCH

The scope of this study is limited to research focused on Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM) and Sustainable Organizational Culture (SOC). Related themes such as job satisfaction, employee well-being, leadership, performance, and organizational development excluded to maintain focus.

Criteria for Article Search

The search strategy in Scopus involved the following keyword queries:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Organizational Culture” AND “Human Resource Management”) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Sustainable human resource management” AND “Organizational Culture”) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Sustainable HRM Practices” AND “sustainable organizational culture”) OR

TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Organizational culture” AND “Sustainability” AND “sustainable HRM”)

The systematic data retrieval process was as follows:

- Step one – Initial search returned 1,266 results.
- Step two – Filtering by period (2010–2025) resulted in 1,091 documents.
- Step three – Applying subject area filters (Business, Management, Accounting, Economics, Econometrics, Finance, and Multidisciplinary) reduced the count to 605 [26].
- Step four – Filtering by document type (Articles and Conference Papers) yielded 495 results.
- Step five – Restricting to English-language documents resulted in 478 final documents, which were included in the bibliometric analysis.

ANALYTICAL MEASUREMENT

This part presents the findings and responses to the study questions mentioned in the introduction section. The graph above (Figure 2) contains interesting details on the research and development of Sustainable Human Resource Management and Sustainable Organizational Culture. The trends are gradually increasing with new ideas and knowledge from 2010 to 2025. The published article in these areas has fluctuated, as 23 in 2010 and highest number 76 were in 2024. These trends started with moderated number in 2010 but the next year only few studies has recorded its number were only 13 documents. There are fluctuation in number of publication in 2011, 2014, 2020 and 2022 but this notion became very important in the eyes of the scholars because its saw notable increase in 2023 to 50 papers, and a significant jump to 76 papers in 2024 and finally 18 paper published in April, 2025. This is not satisfactory result in this field but at the end of the year can be seen more publication.

Figure 1. Total Number of Papers on Sustainable HRM and Sustainable organizational Culture in Scopus from 2010 to 2025(Source: Scopus)

CO-AUTHORSHIP WITH COUNTRY WISE

Title The present study examined international co-authorship patterns by analysing author collaboration using country affiliation as the unit of analysis. A minimum threshold of two publications per country was set to generate the co-authorship network, as recommended by Putri [28]. The relationship between Sustainable Organizational Culture and Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM) remains in its early stages, particularly among the countries listed in Table 2, which shows varying levels of research activity and international linkages.

According to Table 1, the United Kingdom emerged as the most active and interconnected country in this domain, with 1,962 citations and 42 international collaborations. This trend is consistent with broader patterns observed in management research. France follows with 1,198 citations and 16 international links, and China reports 1,037 citations and 23 collaborations. Similarly, the United States has been 970 citations and connected to 42 other countries, indicating a broad and influential research footprint.

Interestingly, India stands out with 763 citations and 21 international collaborations, although its overall research connectivity is lower than that of the United Kingdom. These results reflect a general trend of growing international engagement in management scholarship, where citation volume does not always align with collaboration strength.

As visualized in Figure 2, the co-authorship network highlights international collaborations, with the United Kingdom, United States, France, India, and China forming the core of the global research network in SHRM and organizational culture. These nations demonstrate high impact and strong mutual linkages. Meanwhile, countries like Indonesia, Malaysia, and several European nations (e.g., Italy, Germany, and Poland) participate actively through regionally clustered partnerships.

Conversely, Romania appears relatively isolated in the co-authorship map, showing limited engagement and weak connections to the broader network. The visual network underscores the uneven global distribution of research activity and collaboration, with a concentration of influence among a few central nations. Some countries like Indonesia and Malaysia, and various European nations (e.g., Italy, Germany, and Poland) form different regional clusters, contributing actively through interconnected partnerships. On the other hand, Romania appears isolated with minimal collaboration, linking only weakly to the broader network. The Network highlights the unequal but uneven distribution of research and collaboration in this field.

Table.1 Co-authorship with Country Wise Analysis

country	documents	citations	total link strength
United kingdom	47	1962	42
France	10	1198	16
China	26	1037	23
United states	57	970	24
India	47	763	21
Australia	21	544	25
Turkey	7	500	2
Palestine	2	479	1
Morocco	4	451	2
Italy	14	411	10

Figure2. Network Visualization Co-authorship with Country Wise

D. Keyword Co-occurrence Analysis

Figure 3 presents a keyword co-occurrence, network visualization, illustrating five primary clusters derived from the co-occurrence of keywords within the literature on Sustainable HRM and Sustainable Organizational Culture.

Cluster 1 (Blue) focuses on Human Resource Management, with 31 occurrences. This cluster shows strong associations with keywords such as innovation, corporate culture, performance, digital transformation, and information management. It also links indirectly to sustainability and sustainable organizational culture, indicating a need to further explored the influence of sustainable HRM practices in dynamic and uncertain market environments [29].

Cluster 2 (Green) highlights Organizational Culture with 154 occurrences, directly connected to employee engagement, job satisfaction, leadership, and HRM. However, this cluster notably lacks direct connections with sustainability, suggesting a research gap in linking cultural elements with environmental or social sustainability practices.

Cluster 3 (Red) centres on Sustainability, with 13 occurrences. It connects directly to human resource management, green HRM, organizational culture, HRM practices, and sustainable development, thereby reinforcing the integrative role of sustainability across these domains.

Cluster 4 (Yellow) again emphasizes Organizational Culture, appearing with 79 occurrences and interlinking with HRM, green HRM, knowledge management, sustainability, project management, and HRM practices, showcasing a broader systems-level integration of sustainability values.

Cluster 5 (Purple) is associated with Knowledge Management, with 30 occurrences. It includes interconnections with organizational culture, HRM, green HRM, environmental management, and HRM practices, highlighting its strategic role in fostering sustainable practices.

Overall, the keyword analysis underscores the importance of integrating sustainability into HR and organizational culture frameworks, advocating for stronger alignment between environmental, organizational, and human capital strategies [30].

Figure 3. Network Visualization of Keywords in Sustainable HRM and Sustainable Organizational Culture

E. Bibliographic Coupling Mapping

Figure 4 illustrates the Bibliographic Coupling Map, which explores the interrelationships among documents based on shared citations. The analysis applied a threshold of 25 minimum citations to ensure relevance and clarity, resulting in 86 documents out of 478 being included in the coupling network.

Seven distinct clusters, each color-coded, represent groups of closely related works based on bibliographic similarity:

Cluster 1 (Red): The highest citations were observed for Kusluvan (2010) with 402 citations and a total link strength of 19, followed by Chowdhury (2023) with 401 citations and 15 link strength. Both authors positioned closely, indicating similar reference bases.

Cluster 2 (Green): Steiber (2013) leads this group with 111 citations and 8 link strength.

Cluster 3 (Blue): Benevene (2010) is the central figure with 68 citations and 8 total link strength.

Cluster 4 (Yellow): Masri (2017) emerges as a significant contributor with 434 citations and the highest link strength of 128, suggesting strong integration within the literature network.

Cluster 5 (Purple): Dominated by Roscoe (2019), who has the highest number of citations overall (612) and 62 total link strength, marking this as the most cited node.

Cluster 6 (Aqua): Shokri (2016) stands out with 84 citations and 10 link strength.

Cluster 7 (Orange): The leading document has 65 citations and a link strength of 17.

Notably, D'Cruz (2012) is an outlier in the network with limited connections, indicating isolation from other frequently referenced works. The bibliometric mapping reveals that Cluster 5 holds the highest citation count, while Cluster 4 demonstrates the strongest interlinkage, suggesting both visibility and thematic cohesion among its publications.

Figure 4. Network Visualization

III. CONCLUSION

This study conducted a quantitative bibliometric analysis to examine the relationship between Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM) and Sustainable Organizational Culture (SOC) from 2010 to 2025. Utilizing VOSviewer software, the analysis explored publication trends, international co-authorship networks, keyword co-occurrence, and bibliographic coupling. The findings reveal that the United Kingdom plays a central and highly productive role in this field. However, collaboration between European authors and those from other regions remains limited, suggesting an opportunity to enhance international research partnerships in the domain [31].

The results also indicate that organizational culture-related keywords are not strongly link with sustainability themes, highlighting a conceptual and empirical gap in the integration of SHRM and SOC [32]. Furthermore, the research identifies a lack of a unified theoretical framework, and emphasizes that SHRM remains poorly conceptualized in the context of sustainability [33]. The keyword analysis reinforces the need for industries to better align sustainability principles with HRM practices and organizational culture.

For future research, there is a pressing need to develop a comprehensive framework that combines SHRM and SOC. Further investigations should consider the environmental, social, and economic impacts of SHRM practices across various industries and global regions. Integrative studies involving multiple sectors and geographies will be essential to build robust and generalizable insights.

IV. LIMITATIONS

The analysis was confine to data from the Scopus database. While Scopus provides broad coverage, future studies could incorporate databases such as Web of Science, Google Scholar, and Dimensions for comparative analyses [34].

The study exclusively employed VOSviewer for bibliometric mapping. Alternative tools such as Cite Space, Biblioshiny, and CitNetExplorer could be utilize in future research to enrich the analytical scope.

Keyword selection was limited to terms such as “Sustainable,” “Sustainability,” “Human Resource Management,” “Human Resource Management Practices,” and “Organizational Culture.” This scope excluded emerging topics such as digital transformation, artificial intelligence, and sustainability-driven decision-making, particularly within specific regional or industrial contexts.

The study identified limited connections between sustainable organizational culture and broader sustainability themes. This underscores the under-researched nature of the topic and calls for deeper empirical investigation.

Ultimately, the research underscores the necessity for a unified framework that links SHRM and sustainable organizational culture. This integration is vital for enhancing workplace sustainability, employee well-being, and organizational effectiveness. While this study lays foundational insights into the intersection of SHRM and organizational culture, continued research is crucial to refine strategies, uncover emerging patterns, and advance sustainability practices within the field of business and management.

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